

Correlation of some characteristics of rice varieties grown in saline conditions with grain yield and saline stress index.

Characteristic	Correlation with	
	Grain yield	Saline stress tolerance index
Seed water uptake	0.47*	0.51*
Peroxidase	0.42*	0.69*
Catalase	0.15	0.36
Alpha amylase	0.10	0.11
Beta amylase	0.02	0.15
Total amylase	0.47*	0.15
Seed respiration	-0.18	0.28
Seed redox potential	0.02	0.15
Seed germination	0.68**	0.57*
Seedling height	0.71**	0.72**
Root length	0.62**	0.78**
Seedling fresh weight	0.05	0.26
Seedling dry weight	0.63**	0.66**
Leaf seedling respiration	0.29	0.30
Total water content	0.46*	0.65**
Relative leaf water content	0.57*	0.62**
Transpiration	0.05	0.04
Sap cell concentration	0.02	0.01
Proline content	0.21	0.39
Total chlorophyll content	0.25	0.29
Plant height	0.80***	0.83***
Panicles plant ⁻¹	0.30	0.29
Panicle length	0.32	0.40
Panicle weight	0.81***	0.83***
Filled grains panicle ⁻¹	0.33	0.30
1000-grain weight	0.73**	0.38

* = significant at P=0.05, ** = significant at P=0.01, and *** = significant at P=0.001.

relative leaf water content were highly correlated with the saline stress tolerance index (see table), indicating that measuring varietal ratings for salt tolerance at the early stage of growth via these traits was likely to be effective.

At the late stage of growth, plant height and panicle weight correlated highly and significantly with grain yield under saline conditions, as well as with the saline stress tolerance index, showing that varietal evaluation and indirect selection for grain yield in saline soil via these traits would be an even better method. ■

Multiple submissions. Normally, only one report for a single experiment will be accepted. Two or more items about the same work submitted at the same time will be returned for merging. Submitting at different times multiple notes from the same experiment is highly inappropriate. Detection will result in the rejection of all submissions on that research.

Integrated germplasm improvement — upland

Altamirano, Mandisovi, and Quebracho: new rice cultivars from Argentina

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Altamirano P.A. is, because of its growth duration, tolerance for low temperatures, and good performance on saline and alkaline soils, recommended for sowing in temperate zones or under these soil limitations, according to the new aims of our rice program.

This variety is 0.98 m tall, resists lodging, and has intermediate threshability. It reaches maturity in 133 d and its yield potential is 8,000 kg ha⁻¹. The caryopsis is 7.47 mm long and 2.79 mm wide and the ratio of length to width is 2.67, matching that of the commercial type.

Its endosperm has a medium amylose content (21%) and an intermediate gelatinization temperature. Its protein content is 8.35%. It is moderately resistant to *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav.

This variety originated from the cross of experimental line H-115-19-1 and variety Yerua P.A. to obtain the highest quality of grain, yield, and *P. grisea* Cav. resistance. Line H-115-19-1 came from the cross of varieties Dawn and Zenith. Crossing was carried out by the rice program at the Ing. Agr. Julio Hirschhorn Experiment Station. A combination of mass and pedigree selection was used.

Because of its earliness, Altamirano was released for cultivation in areas near 30 °S in Buenos Aires Province.

Mandisovi P.A. was bred to satisfy the demand for aromatic rices, which, unlike La Calendaria FA, has a caryopsis that corresponds to the long-wide type. It can be consumed both as polished or integral rice (this alone or mixed with red pericarp rice).

Mandisovi is 0.83 m tall, resists lodging, and reaches maturity in 135 d. Its yield potential is 6,000 kg ha⁻¹ and it has intermediate threshability. Mandisovi's caryopsis is 7.64 mm long and 2.7 mm wide and its ratio of length to width is 2.82.

The endosperm contains an intermediate amylose content (23%) and low gelatinization temperature. Its protein content is 8.80% and it has a weak aroma. Mandisovi has moderate resistance to *P. oryzae* Cav.

This variety was obtained by crossing African cultivar Chocoto and H161-18/ /desc./ 80-17. Line H161-18 was developed by crossing IR1103-15-10 and Calady 40 sel. FA to obtain earliness and high protein content. The crossing was carried out by the rice program. A combination of mass and pedigree selection was used. The target area for diffusion is 32 °S near Villaguay City.

Quebracho P.A. is the first Argentine cultivar of the long-wide type, and it is aromatic and has a red pericarp. This release aimed to satisfy an increasing interest in the consumption of special rices. It is consumed as integral grain, alone or combined with similar rices of normal pericarp.

Quebracho is 0.89 m tall and resists lodging. It reaches maturity in 145 d and yields 7,000 kg ha⁻¹. It has intermediate threshability. The caryopsis is 8.1 mm long and 2.75 mm wide, and its ratio of length to width is 2.94.

For quality, it is important to mention its medium amylose content (22%) and its intermediate gelatinization temperature. Its protein content is 9.68% and it is strongly aromatic. Quebracho is resistant to *P. oryzae* Cav.

This cultivar was developed by crossing Chocoto and H161-18/ /desc./ 80-17, in a crossing carried out by the rice program. A combination of mass and pedigree selection was used. The probable target area is 32 °S near Villaguay City. ■